

An Empirical Research on the Relationship between Entrepreneurship Tendency and Using of Social Media of University Students

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship tendencies of university students are nearly ubiquitous, while there has been little analysis of the effects of social media using on entrepreneurship tendencies in the literature. The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between the habit of social media using and entrepreneurship tendencies of university students. The research problem involves two variables. The first one is social media which is an important determinant of social and business life. The second one is the tendency of candidates who wish to become entrepreneurs. The sample group consisted of students, who took lesson of entrepreneurship, from Mersin and Ahi Evran Universities and took place during the academic year of 2014-2015. The data was collected through an online questionnaire that is reformed by authors with reference to Chye-Koh (1996), Quan-Haase and Young (2010), as 60 items, and then 567 students take part in the sample with convenience sampling method. There are two suitable methods that could have been used for this research; the correlation and regression analyses. The data gathered has been analyzed using statistical packaged software and the results will be introduced with suggestions and comments. The validity and reliability of the data collection tool has been confirmed after analyzing the collected data with statistical methods ($p < 0,05$ and $p < 0,01$). The results are interpreted within the framework of the research problem. As a result of the conducted analysis, statistical significant relationships were found between the two variables ($r:0,474$; $p > 0,01$). Finally, the regression analysis results are seen important for researchers, professionals, and those interested in these fields.

Keywords: Social Media; Uses and Gratifications Theory; Entrepreneur; Entrepreneurship Tendencies.

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurial tendencies are referred to as characteristics that make one person an entrepreneur and another one not an entrepreneur. These are personality characteristics and environmental forces that shape individuals' behavior and determine whether they will or will not engage in entrepreneurial activities (Davidsson, 1995). So, individualistic beliefs about entrepreneurship are as important as the other production resources.

Focus on entrepreneurship has revealed that both the nature and the role of entrepreneurs are essential for economic growth and business development (Acs, 2006). Because of this scope, entrepreneur and entrepreneurship is defined differently by various scholars. Brockhaus (1982) defines entrepreneur as "a major owner and manager of a business venture not employed elsewhere", and Hisrich and Peter (2002) defines entrepreneurship as "the creation of value through the establishment of organizations". The most common defining of entrepreneurship is seen as "a process of starting and running one's own business" (Katundu and Gabagambi, 2014). In this sense, entrepreneurship can regard to have contribution towards self-sufficiency, employment creation and wealth for individuals and nation.

The integration process of production factors is needed to focus cognitive abilities of entrepreneur. Entrepreneurial decision making period starts with entrepreneurial tendencies which are referred to motivation about being an entrepreneur or not. This is so powerful period to catch an opportunity creation about business, and explain why some people recognize and exploit entrepreneurial factors. Namely "effectuation" and "causation" are main entrepreneurial decision making modes and reflect extremes of the mental frameworks about entrepreneur (Sarasvathy, 2001).

When entrepreneur pursues the opportunities, he or she uses the resources with the help of the effectuation processes. Because some critical questions about resources are answered with this period such as which they are, what they know and whom they know. The effectual logic focuses on affordable loss, strategic alliances and seeks to control an unpredictable future. Because opportunity creating processes are still flexible and allowing the entrepreneur to take advantage of environmental contingencies (Fisher, 2012). On the other side, an individual makes choices based on his pre-existing knowledge as well as all possible information related to the problem at hand in a causation mode (Sarasvathy, 2001). According to Chandler et al. (2011) an entrepreneur using causal logic will begin with a given goal, focus on expected returns, emphasize competitive analyses, exploit pre-existing knowledge and try to predict an uncertain future. Because of the causation mode is about the analytical approach towards achieving the desired goals and outcomes, it is associated with a moving spectrum of opportunity creation, rather than detecting and recognizing opportunities with highest expected returns (Baron and Ensley 2006). So it means that different entrepreneurs who face high uncertainty are likely to form different perceptions about potential opportunities and possible effects, which vary according to the entrepreneurial contexts.

Kirzner (1997) emphasizes that opportunity recognition is a function of idiosyncratic information, knowledge and social capital possesses by individual entrepreneurs, as well as the uneven distribution of economic resources, thus the presence of unexploited market opportunity waiting to be discovered. This perspective brings entrepreneur into critical importance because of his cognitive process which includes entrepreneurship tendency.

Under the purview of entrepreneurship recognition, extant studies demonstrate how learning process influences entrepreneurship tendency (Politis, 2005), how previous experience can effect to recognize new opportunities (Littunen, 2000), making problem-solving style easier through network with others (Buttner and Gryskiewicz, 1993). Also, some other factors can affect the entrepreneurship tendency such as demographic factors which include genetic, sex, education, parent's situations and income (Sexton and Bowman-Upton, 1990; Nicolaou et al. 2008); psychological factors which include the need for achievement, locus of control, risk-taking propensity, tolerance of ambiguity, self-confidence and innovativeness (Chye-Koh, 1996). In addition to individual and environmental factors, there are also push and pull factors for extant employee in a firm such as unemployment, money, prosperity and reputation.

If needed to clarify the psychological factors, it can be said that all factors affect different subsystem about entrepreneurship tendency. The need for achievement is about the motivation of being entrepreneur, taking controlled risk, increasing skills of problem-solving and setting the goals. Locus of control has two dimensions known as internal and external locus of control (Hansemark, 1998). According to the studies, entrepreneur has internal locus of control because it includes talents and effort about a new business while external locus includes fortune and chance (Kaufmann, et al., 1995). About risk taking propensity, there is an expectation that entrepreneurs can take risk more than others. Therefore, entrepreneur is defined as a risk-taken person and he can take advantage by using risks. Tolerance of ambiguity is ability about being positive in the uncertain circumstances. Because ambiguity is not a threat, it is actually an opportunity for new owner of business in unspecific environmental conditions (Schere, 1982).

Self-confidence is not only a psychological characteristic but also a skill of entrepreneur, because entrepreneur has to achieve goals with positive beliefs and empathy. He believes that his business ideas are better than others and he feels free from fear, doubt. Also he has feeling of trust on himself and tries to have a state of trustful relationship (Boyd and Vozikis, 1994). Innovativeness gives the entrepreneur chance for a different business or service, after the research process. Because, entrepreneur creates new combinations of all factors, and then presents to the market for assessment by consumers, as an innovator (Vozikis and Gryskiewicz, 1993). In some situations, innovativeness can be about new products or services and other situations it can be new techniques and new information or multiple of all.

Not only economic and legal conditions but also psychological factors have great importance in understanding and fostering entrepreneurship and assessing entrepreneurship tendency or potential. For this reason this study focuses on students in Mersin and Ahi Evran University. Through their education, business students acquire the technical tools for founding and running a business. This study explores the extent to which business students in Mersin and Ahi Evran University possess entrepreneurship tendency. According to Fagbohunge and Jayeoba (2012), entrepreneurial potential is the extent to which an individual possesses the characteristics that are associates with successful entrepreneurs. So it can be said that entrepreneurship tendency can be affected by different internal and external variables of entrepreneurship nature.

Technology is one of these external variables and it has strong power to change all process about business. Technology brings great facility for life, although it has some disadvantage for people. Communication, joint venture and transportation practices have been fulfilled globally. Social media gives user chance to create social interaction via highly accessibly web-based technologies. These social interactions are created through wide range of platforms such as blogs, social networking sites, wikis, micro-blogging services and multimedia sharing services. Social media includes but is not limited to these tools, because it is often associated such concepts as user-generated content, crowd sourcing, and Web 2.0. Basically, social media has four major potential strengths which include empowerment, collaboration, participation and time for entrepreneurs. It is defined by social interaction as well as it is seen cooperative and participation tools for media because of its very nature (Bertot et al., 2010). Not only can users connect with each other and other communities to share information, but also they can achieve a common goal and interest. Because it provides the ability to speak and it can empower users to communicate each other. Also, accessing to the internet is an inexpensive way to broadcast or publish information. In near real time, users can use technologies to share everything immediately. According to the uses and gratifications theory, the main reason of using social media is satisfy the needs (Katz et al., 1973). So, people chose and personalize the social media tools by considering their needs. After choosing the tools, people take an active role in social media for sociability, pastime, relaxation, obtaining information (Quan-Haase and Young, 2010).

From macro to micro level, all kind of business activities vary with social platform. For example, entrepreneur who is a knowledge seeker and creative thinker can use social media for existing idea or product and turning it into something better. Also entrepreneur use information technology for search information that is relevant to making and growing his business. When an entrepreneur gains inspiration about a business idea, he needs to confidence himself and team members. Also a promoter is necessary to encourage him make decision based on observed or anticipated effect on profit. During the making business idea real, difficult, even seemingly insurmountable obstacles must be overcome by entrepreneur. Instinctively, talents of relationship-builder are needed for sustainability and managing high-risk situations in creating process (Hisrich and Peters, 2002). From the beginning to the end of all processes, social media provides an advantage such as extending to the broad markets, attracting the consumers and transporting wide distribution.

Social networks are about experiences as well as web sites, because they give vision through the interconnectedness of online social media combined with traditional media. Schultz (2007) explains all these interrelations with term of social media ecosystem. This ecosystem is very dynamic universe of tools and channels both individuals and companies. Entrepreneur will try to weave through this universe, whether he wants to own his business and keep in touch team members, retailers and customers or other interest groups. Social media ecosystem is comprised of photo and video sites, presence, blogosphere, offline events, wikis, social media tools, social networks. Basic assumption of this ecosystem is changing dynamics of interactions between companies, costumers and individuals. Disparately, individuals can influence the product process. Also their opinions can be affected by the social platform and other technological advancements. Because social media is one of the most important factors of changing world with three media types as owned media, paid media and earned media. These media types refer the relationships between owner of business and media. Owned media can be controlled by entrepreneur or company web-site, paid media is bought by the entrepreneur as sponsorships and advertising, earned media is an uncontrolled way.

There is no need to have elaborate budgets while using social media unlike traditional media. Entrepreneur can develop communication strategies that both reach and engage people in myriad ways on cheap and creative platforms. Also social media platforms provide extensive opportunities to customize user engagement and transport

the goods (Hanna et al., 2011). Because of these advances, science world gives social media important consideration increasingly. Then, there are different studies and social media ecosystem besides. All studies have their own perspective; some of them have individualistic approach, while others are social.

Correa et al. (2010) study, as the individual, suggests that personality of users have relationship with social-media. The results of the study show extraversion dimension of personality is an important predictor of social media use. In education literature, Kitsantas and Dabbagh (2011) suggest that social media has a potential about integrating formal and informal learning, so social media and self-regulated learning has relationship. Shirky (2011) handles the term as a social approach and remark the political power of social media because of its public effects. Fischer and Reuber (2011) posit that twitter-based interaction can trigger effectual cognitions, but that high levels of interaction via this medium can lead to effectual churn. So they emphasize that perceived time affordability can predict the level of social interaction in which an entrepreneur engages via Twitter. It means that social media tools like twitter are seen as a viable marketing tool for social media entrepreneur. Finally, Wallsten and Rhyan (2014) notice that the use of social media by firms is nearly ubiquitous while there has been little analysis of its effectiveness in small business succeed. They choose mobile food firms that have social media business model and investigate the relationship between sustainability of firms and using frequency of social media. The results of the research show that using of Facebook, twitter and other social media tools affect firms' ability to stay in business.

From this point of view, it is wondered that there is a relationship between entrepreneurship tendencies and social media in this study. For analyzing of entrepreneurship tendencies, psychological factors are used. Also, for measuring of the social media four sub dimensions are used as sociability, pastime, relaxation and obtaining information with reference to uses and gratifications theory. Methodology and model of the study is given the next title, and then results, conclusions and recommendations take part in the study.

2. Objectives and Hypotheses

The objective of the study is to examine the relationship between the habit of social media using and entrepreneurship tendencies of university students. The research problem involves two variables. The first one is social media which has four sub dimensions as sociability, pastime, relaxation and obtaining information. The second variable is entrepreneurship tendency. Also, it is investigated that whether there is an effect of social media on entrepreneurship tendency or not. There one main hypothesis in this study that there are positive relations between the habit of social media using and entrepreneurship tendency significantly. Also, it is tested that social media has an effect on entrepreneurship tendency in students of business.

Fig 1: The Model of the Research

3. Methodology

In methodology part, some information takes part about participant, data collection tools, procedure and data analysis. After this part, findings, conclusion and recommendations are discussed finally in this study.

3.1. Participants

All participants are a number of 567 business students at Mersin and Ahi Evran University who take the lesson of entrepreneurship. The single condition of research is taking the entrepreneurship lesson before. So the other demographic factors are ignored such as sex, class, home town.

3.2. Data Collection Tools

40 entrepreneurship tendency items take part first section of the survey. Then, in the second section of the survey, there are 19 social media items which includes 6 items for sociability, 5 items for pastime, 4 items for relaxation and 4 items for obtaining information. And one question is about taking entrepreneurship lesson before or not. Entrepreneurship tendency scale is developed by Chye-Koh (1996) and also it is used by Avşar (2007) for

university students. Social media scale is developed by Quan-Haase and Young (2010) and it is also used by Akçay (2011) with reference to uses and gratifications theory. The instruments were applied together to business students in March and April of 2015. Participants were informed about the objective of the study and were presented with detailed training of instruments used.

3.3. Data Analysis

The data collected via the questionnaires have been analyzed statistically with arithmetic mean, Pearson correlation analysis, stepwise multiple linear regressions on the computer using statistical program.

4. Findings

The cronbach's alpha results of analysis are summarized in table 1, which includes entrepreneurship tendency and social media scale. Also the cronbach's alpha of sub dimensions of social media are given in the same table. As is seen from the table, the cronbach's alpha is above 0.7 for all scale which is an acceptable reliability coefficient.

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha of Variables

Scale	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Entrepreneurship Tendency	40	0,718
Social Media	19	0,899
• Sociability	6	0,894
• Pastime	5	0,807
• Relaxation	4	0,915
• Obtaining Information	4	0,793

According to the descriptive statistics of entrepreneurship tendency, data is distributed in the range of 3,35 and 4,41. Standard deviations which are a measure of how spread out numbers are distributed in the range of 0,809 and 1,914. In the entrepreneurship scale, data has very similar points in 21th item, while it separates in 9th item. In social media scale, the means of scale is in the range of 2,19 and 3,76 and the highest standard deviation is 0,901 in 17th item, while the lowest one is 1,603 in 4th item. So, data has similar points in 17th item, while it clusters separately in 4th item. Also for descriptive analysis, it is needed to test of kurtosis and skewness to understand the data has a normal distribution or not. Statistically, skewness is the range of +-2 and kurtosis is the range of +-7, so it shows a normal distribution. Thus, the scale of the research has a normal distribution in this study.

After the descriptive statistics of entrepreneurship tendency and social media, the correlations between variables are given table 2. Sociability, pastime, relaxation and obtaining information are taken part as sub-dimensions of social media and also there are the correlations between these sub-dimensions of social media and entrepreneurship tendency in table 2.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Analysis of the Relations between Entrepreneurship Tendency and Sub-Dimensions of Social Media

Variables	1	2	3	4	Ent.Tend.
1.Sociability	1				
2.Pastime	0,244**	1			
3.Relaxation	0,402**	0,494**	1		
4.Obtaining Information	0,344**	0,260**	0,136	1	
Entrepreneurship Tendency	0,257**	0,059*	0,118*	0,167**	1

*Correlation $p < 0,05$ (two tailed); **Correlation $p < 0,01$ (two tailed)

Direct correlation between “entrepreneurship tendency” and “social media” is 0,474 (p:0,000). According to the table, nearly all variables have correlation with themselves with p:0,000, except “relaxation” sub dimensions. Relaxation has 0,118 correlation with “entrepreneurship tendency” with 95% confidence and there is not any statistically significant relationship between “relaxation” and “obtaining information”. Also “pastime” and “entrepreneurship tendency” has 0,059 correlations with 95% confidence, so all other variables have correlations with p:000.

For testing the validity and meaning of the model, the value of F, R as the correlation value and R2 as the regression value are given in table 3. Also for testing the hypothesis, the Beta value, which is a measure of how strongly each predictor variable influences the criterion variable, and regression models are seen in the table 3.

Table 3: Regression Analysis of Entrepreneurship Tendency and Social Media

Variables	Beta	t	Sig.	R	R ²	F	Sig.F
1. Regression Model							
Constant	0,4986	3,930	0,004				
Social Media	0,6897	9,426	0,00010				
				0,7038	0,4949	88,852	,000 ^a

Regression Model : $Y_{(\text{Entrepreneurship Tendency})} = 0,4986 + 0,686(S_{\text{Social Media}})$.

According to the table, social media is a predictor of entrepreneurship tendency with R2:0,494 (p:0,000). Also for detailing the analysis, the multiple regression results of sub-dimensions of social media and entrepreneurship tendency are given table 4.

Table 4: Regression Analysis of Entrepreneurship Tendency and Sub-dimensions of Social Media

Variables	Beta	t	Sig.	R	R ²	F	Sig.F
Regression Model: $Y_{(\text{Entrepreneurship Tendency})} = 3,544 + 0,169(S_{\text{Sociability}}) + 0,011(P_{\text{Pastime}}) + 0,079(R_{\text{Relaxation}}) + 0,015(O_{\text{Obtaining Information}})$							
Constant	3,544	8,809	0,000				
Sociability	0,169	-0,631	0,015				
Pastime	0,011	0,741	0,730				
Relaxation	0,079	0,907	0,216				
Obtaining Information	0,015	-0,071	0,043				
				0,409	0,168	4,401	0,009

According to the table 4, the model of the research is acceptable statistically. The F value, which is about the validity of model, is 4,401 and p is 0,009. According to the result of F test, the value of F is higher than ±1,96 points, and p is lowest than 0,005, so the model is validity and statistically significant. After the validity, correlation and regression points are examined to see the relation and effect between variables. The correlation is 0,409 for this model and regression is 0,168, so there is a significant effect of social media on entrepreneurship tendency. Because the regression value is the range of 0 and 1, so the model of social media and entrepreneurship tendency is validity and the effect is acceptable.

The title of the research is about the relationship between social media and entrepreneurship tendency, so the hypothesis of the study is there is relationship between two variables. But after the testing relations between variables, it is wondered the effect of social media on entrepreneurship tendency, so the regression analysis is taken part in the final section of the study. The regression results show that the model about social media and entrepreneurship tendency is validity and social media is a predictor of entrepreneurship tendency significantly.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The technological progress can affect social, economic and environmental factors such as culture, family life and jobs. These effects lead some changes the way of thinking and decision making, so the characteristic of people also become different in time. The young generations can be observed easily from students of university to see the changes of life style. In social life, technology changes the style of communication and obtaining information, this effect is also seen in the business life. Entrepreneurs feel this effect in two ways; firstly he or she is a person who wants to create his own job, so his character and other psychological feature such as cognitive abilities, problem solving methods and skills are formed by the structure of society, family and other inner factors in the shade of recent developments. Secondly, the entrepreneur brings together natural, human and capital resources to produce foods or services to be provided by his business, so all product system moves with the times. The university students are potential candidates of entrepreneur, so their entrepreneurship tendency can give important results for researches.

Entrepreneurial tendency is about the characteristics that make one person an entrepreneur and another one not an entrepreneur. And this tendency can be connected a lot of inner and outer factors, it is wondered in this study that there is a relationship between entrepreneurship tendency and social media significantly. According to the correlation results, there is a significant relationship between two variables ($r:0,474$; $p>0,01$). Also social media has four sub dimensions as sociability, pastime, relaxation, obtaining information and these sub-dimensions are significant correlation with entrepreneurship tendency in this sample. All correlation is $p:0,000$ except sub dimension of relaxation, it has $0,118$ correlation with entrepreneurship tendency in 95% confidence and it has not any relation with obtaining information. So the hypothesis of study is accepted, there is a significant relationship between social media and entrepreneurship tendency. The validity and reliability of the scale is in the requested level. Also it is wondered that the social media is a predictor of entrepreneurship tendency or not in the study. So to test this effect, a model of regression is created and analyzed. According to the regression model, social media is a predictor of entrepreneurship tendency with $0,494$ R square ($p:0,000$). Also the sub dimensions of social media have effect on entrepreneurship tendency ($p:0,000$). In the regression model of sub dimensions, pastime ($p:0,730$) and relaxation ($p:0,216$) have not significant value, while sociability ($p: 0,015$) and obtaining information ($p: 0,043$) are acceptable.

Summary below results, there is a significant relationship between social media and entrepreneurship tendency. Also, social media is a predictor of entrepreneurship tendency. But only sub-dimensions of sociability and obtaining information are predictors of entrepreneurship tendency, while the other sub-dimensions as pastime and relaxation are not. The need of sociability and obtaining information is also obligation for entrepreneurs to risk their money and time for making the business idea real and making profit. So the result of study shows that social media can help the entrepreneur to organize his business well to be successful by obtaining information and social environment. The pastime and relaxation functions of social media are needed for fun and psychological wellness, so it is not about entrepreneurship directly. So it can be suggested that social media can be used for entrepreneurial process for practices. Also the other technological outcomes and innovations can be researched to bring light the entrepreneurship education and literature.

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